

1983 in Guangdong Province, China. Eight plant species grown in pots were confined with 1-5 viruliferous zigzag leafhoppers *Recilia dorsalis* Motsch per plant until the vector died (34 d). Maize plants also were inoculated with green leafhopper *Nephotettix cincticeps*. Disease symptoms developed 15-25 d after inoculation. Plants without symptoms were observed for 5-6 mo.

GDV infected wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), oat (*Avena sativa*), wild rice (*Oryza rufipogon*), Japanese grass (*Alopecurus aequalis*), and maize (*Zea mays*). Small galls developed on field grass (*Leptochloa chinensis*), but further confirmation is needed. *Echinochloa crus-galli* and *Leersia hexandra* did not have virus symptoms (see table).

Maize is a new host of GDV. Both zigzag and green leafhoppers

Host range of GDV in Guangdong, China, 1983.^a

Host	Zigzag leafhopper per plant	Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (no.)
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	1	17	2
<i>Avena sativa</i>	1	15	3
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	4	6	3
<i>Alopecurus aequalis</i>	5	3	2
	3	12	1
<i>Zea mays</i>	7	5	1
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	3	5	small galls
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	3	5	0
	3	5	0
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	1	15	0

^a*Nephotettix cincticeps* were used to inoculate the virus.

transmitted GDV to maize. Symptoms developed 28 d after inoculation. Small, light green galls appeared on the leaf veins, enlarged, and became waxy white. Some galls formed vein swellings up to

1.5 cm long and 0.25 cm wide. Stunting was not serious. The results were confirmed when rice plants exhibited typical symptoms after back-inoculation. *ℵ*

Rice diseases on the Godavari Delta

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We surveyed rice disease status in 1983 rabi, 1984 kharif, and 1984 rabi in East

and West Godavari Districts. Surveyors visited 69 villages and talked with 86 farmers in West Godavari, and visited 31 villages and talked with 35 farmers in East Godavari.

- Blast (BI), which only occurs in rabi, sheath blight (ShB), and

bacterial blight were major diseases, and caused substantial yield losses.

- Tungro (RTV) occurs sporadically, but southern coastal districts had RTV epidemics in 1984 kharif.
- IR50 is highly susceptible to BI. Applying heavy N doses (60-140 kg N/ha) increased BI disease seventy. Rabi varieties BPT1235 and IR62 have BI resistance (see table).
- Stem rot caused by *Sclerotium oryzae*, brown spot caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae*, and sheath rot caused by *Acrocyldrium oryzae* were sometimes observed, but caused negligible losses. *ℵ*

Disease incidence^a on different rices in Andhra Pradesh, India, 1983-84.

Variety	Disease incidence				
	Bacterial blight	Blast	Tungro	Sheath blight	Stem rot
			<i>Rabi</i>		
IR50	–	VS	–	M	–
IET1444	M	–	S	–	SL
BPT1235	SL	SL	M	S	–
IR62	–	M	–	S	–
RP6-17	–	SL	M	–	SL
Prabhat	–	–	SL	–	–
IR36	–	M	–	–	–
Mahsuri	–	–	–	–	–
MTU5 249	–	–	–	M	–
			<i>Kharif</i>		
MTU7029	SL	–	–	S	–
MTU5249	–	–	–	–	M
MTU4870	–	–	–	M	–
MTU2077	M	–	–	M	–
MTU2067	M	–	–	M	–
RP6-17	–	–	–	M	–
MTU6024	SL	–	–	M	–
IR42	SL	–	–	–	–
Jaya	SL	–	–	–	–
Mahsuri	SL	–	–	–	–
Swarna Mahsuri	SL	–	–	–	–
IR62	M	–	–	S	–

^a SL = slight, M = moderate, S = severe, VS = very severe.

BR3 reaction to multiple disease infection

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Rice fields often are infected by more than one disease. We evaluated BR3 under multiple disease infection. BR3 seedlings were transplanted in 48 rows of 10 hills each. The field received the recommended 80-60-40 kg NPK/ha.